

Replicative δ Polymerases from Plants and Animals Possess Very Similar Polymerase, Proofreading and Regulatory Domains

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Abstract

In eukaryotes, genome replication starts with the initiation of replication by the primases, followed by the synthesis of the leading- and lagging-strands by two different replicative DNA polymerases (pols), viz. ϵ and δ , respectively. The polymerase and proofreading (PR) active sites of the δ pols are analyzed from various animal and plant sources by multiple sequence alignment (MSA). The animal and plant δ pols are found to possess almost identical polymerase and PR domains. However, the BLASTp analysis has shown only 56.57% identity between the plant (*Arabidopsis thaliana*) and animal (human) δ pols. The template-binding pair (-YG-), the catalytic amino acid (K) and the nucleotide selection amino acid (Q) are found to be the same in both plant and animal δ pols. The δ pols from plant and animal sources contain a typical Mg^{2+} -binding motif, (-YGD₂D-) in the polymerase domain and 2 possible Zn^{2+} -binding motifs (ZBMs) in their carboxy terminal domain (CTD). One of the ZBMs binds to the 4Fe-4S cluster and is suggested to be involved in the regulation of replication. Interestingly, the invariant -SLYPS- and -YGD₂D- motifs which are found in the δ pols are not found in the other replicative pol ϵ . Furthermore, both animal and plant δ pols use the same PR exonuclease active site amino acids, and thus, belong to the DEDD(Y)-superfamily of exonucleases, as found in other DNA pols. Besides, many specialized, conserved sequence motifs are also identified and discussed.

Keywords: Eukaryotic genome replication; DNA polymerases δ ; δ DNA polymerase active site; Proofreading exonucleases; Proofreading exonuclease active sites; *Arabidopsis thaliana*; *Homo sapiens*

1. Introduction

Duplication of genomes is an indispensable activity in the life-cycle of all living organisms to preserve and maintain the blueprint of life in all living cells. Therefore, high-fidelity genome replication is fundamental to all life forms. The genome of each organism encodes several DNA pols which are involved in genome replication as well as repair mechanisms. To date, five different DNA pols have been characterized in *Escherichia coli*, eight in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, and as many as 16 in humans [1]. However, only three DNA pols, viz. α , δ and ϵ , also known as replicative polymerases, are involved in the duplication of the nuclear genome in all eukaryotes [2]. Whereas the pol α is involved in the synthesis of the primers to initiate the genome replication process, the other two replicative pols, viz. pol δ and pol ϵ faithfully replicate the whole genome and make an exact copy of the original genome. All three replicative polymerases belong to B-family pols (B pols) which are involved not only in replication but also in repair of any error occurring during the replication process [3]. The B-family DNA pols are reported from both prokaryotes and eukaryotes, e.g., pol II, pol B, pol α , pol ϵ , pol δ , pol ζ . The B-family DNA pols, in addition to polymerization, exhibit 3'→5' PR function [4]. The structural and functional aspects of these pols from animals, yeasts and higher fungi have been extensively analyzed and reported by Palanivelu [5, 6]. Even though more than a dozen different DNA pols are reported from plant cells to perform various replicative and repair functions, detailed properties about them are still very limited. All the replicative pols have an efficient PR function. However, mutations that escape during the replication process, but rarely, generate the most important new genetic variants in animals and plants.

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Though the replication process is highly conserved in all domains of life, it is much more complex in eukaryotes [7]. Genome replication in eukaryotes is incredibly more sophisticated and is performed by a highly coordinated series of molecular events. The replication process, apart from the replicative DNA pols, depends on the participation of many enzymes and regulatory proteins, like primases, cell-cycle kinases, replicative helicases, single-strand binding proteins (SSBs), additional repair enzymes, ligases, etc. Given the importance of accurate DNA replication, the proper function of all these enzymes is critical to maintaining the genome stability.

Initiation, the very first-step in the replication process in both prokaryotes and eukaryotes, is accomplished by a multi-structural enzyme-protein complex, known as a primosome. The primosome essentially consists of an origin-of-replication initiator protein, a replicative helicase, a helicase loader, SSBs, a primase, etc. [5]. After successful priming of replication, the replication process is taken over by the replisomes by the next multi-protein complex. The replisome is mainly composed of two different replicative DNA pols in eukaryotes, viz. pol δ and pol ϵ . In this step, the DNA primers synthesized by DNA pol α (pol1) at the initiation step, are further extended to completion by these replicative pols. In prokaryotes and eukaryotes, the crucial step of the initiation of replication is performed by an RNA primase, but an additional DNA primase is required for eukaryotic replications which is synthesized by the DNA pol α . The leading-strand is synthesized by DNA pol ϵ (pol2), and the lagging-strand is synthesized by DNA pol δ (pol3). In contrast to the continuous leading strand synthesis, the lagging strand is synthesized discontinuously in ~ 200 nucleotides (nt)-long Okazaki fragments, which are then ligated to form the contiguous lagging strand [8].

1.1. Various Activities of the DNA pol δ during Genome Replication

The DNA pol δ is a high-fidelity enzyme, catalyzing the nucleotidyl transfer reaction with an error frequency of 1/22,000 [9]. Replication is initiated by pol α , priming on both strands. On the lagging strand, the priming is repeated at multiple points, whereas only once on the leading strand. During the synthesis of the lagging-strand, pol δ synthesizes a large number of Okazaki fragments (OFs) right up to the 5'-end of a preceding RNA primer, whereupon it is recycled to a new primer terminus, leaving behind a nick or a short gap. Pol δ is also responsible for maturation of the previously synthesized OFs by gradually removing the RNA primers (one at a time from the 5'-end) by a proliferating cell nuclear antigen (PCNA)-bound Flap endonuclease 1 (FEN1) which are gradually filled in the same order with dNTPs to produce ligatable links which are ligated by a ligase to make the continuous lagging strand. In addition to its function in DNA replication, pol δ has been shown to play important roles in DNA mismatch repair and recombination events also [10]. Thus, the multifunctional nature of DNA pol δ appears to be a crucial determinant of the overall fidelity of the DNA replication process in eukaryotes [11]. Even though the DNA pols δ have been extensively studied from yeasts, higher fungal and animal sources, not much information is available from plant sources.

1.2. Subunit Composition and Structural Features of human and plant δ Pols

DNA pol δ (pol3) has been extensively studied from the yeast, *S. cerevisiae*, and humans. In addition to its role in chromosomal DNA replication (as mentioned earlier where it performs the lagging-strand synthesis), it is also involved in DNA repair, DNA/RNA primer removal and recombination functions as mentioned above. Pol δ is a multi-subunit protein complex, composed of a catalytic subunit and 3 accessory subunits. The latter subunits play a critical role in the regulation of pol δ functions. The catalytic subunit of human pol δ (polD1) is one of the most well-studied. It is composed of 1107 amino acid residues and harbours the polymerase and PR exonuclease domains. Both the domains are separated by ~ 45 Å [12]. The human DNA pol δ is a heterotetramer, structurally very similar to the DNA pol ϵ (Fig. 1a). (In the budding yeast *S. cerevisiae*, the enzyme is made up of only three subunits; the p12 kDa subunit was not found [13].

Figure 1a Subunit structure of the DNA pol δ from humans

Adapted from [6, 13].

The numbers in brackets denote the approximate molecular mass of the subunits.

Fig. 1b shows the organization of various domains of the pol δ from humans.

Figure 1b A schematic diagramme showing the domain organization of the DNA pol δ of animals (The numberings are from the human enzyme)

NTD, N-Terminal Domain; Exo, PR Exonuclease domain; PIP, PCNA Interacting Peptide (During elongation, the PCNA (the replication clamp) increases the pol δ catalytic rate by >30-fold. In fact, pol δ shows little activity in the absence of PCNA); A and B are CysA and CysB ZBMs.

Pol δ from *Arabidopsis*, like animals and fission yeast, is composed of four subunits (POLD1–POLD4) [10]. The POLD1 catalytic subunit harbours both the polymerase and PR exonuclease domains and it is highly stimulated by the PCNA. The other subunits in the complex are involved not only in the stabilization of the polymerase complex, but also in its interactions with the PCNA. In *Arabidopsis*, as in other eukaryotes, the deletion of *POLD1* and *POLD2* genes is found to be lethal. The subunit structure of the plant, *A. thaliana*, is shown in Fig. 2a. These data confirm that the subunit composition of the replicative pol δ is highly conserved in plants and is very similar to animal enzymes.

Figure 2a Subunit structure of the DNA pol δ from plants (*A. thaliana*). The numbers in brackets denote the approximate molecular mass of the subunits. NB: Rice has two *POLD4* genes.

Fig. 2b shows a tentative arrangement of various domains on the catalytic subunit, POLD1.

Figure 2b A schematic diagramme showing the domain organization of DNA pol δ from *A. thaliana*

PIP, PCNA Interacting Peptide (During elongation, the PCNA (the replication clamp) increases the pol δ catalytic activity several folds; A and B are CysA and CysB ZBMs.

1.3. Genome Replication in Plant Cells

Replication defects in plants may affect various functions like genome stability, plant growth, flowering, pollination, yield, etc. Our knowledge of DNA replication in plant cells is mostly derived from yeasts and animals. As in animals, the genome replication in plants is accomplished by a large multi-protein complex system known as the replisome. Some of the equivalent replisome proteins and enzymes that have already been characterized from plant sources are the minichromosome maintenance protein complex (MCM), replicative helicase, cell division cycle protein 45 (CDC45), proliferating cell nuclear antigen (PCNA), replication factor C (RFC), replication protein A (RPA), flap endonuclease, ligase, etc. [14]. It is interesting to note that in *Arabidopsis*, the knockout mutants of the main subunits of these two replicative pols (pol ϵ and δ) are found to be lethal.

The primase (DNA pol α) and the other replicative pols ϵ and δ from animal sources have been analyzed and reported by this author [5, 6]. In this communication, the DNA replicative pol δ from plant sources is analyzed and reported.

2. Material and methods

The protein sequence data of animal and plant DNA δ pols were obtained from PUBMED and SWISS-PROT databases. The advanced version of Clustal Omega was used for protein sequence analysis. Along with the conserved motifs identified by the bioinformatics analysis and from the data already available from biochemical, SDM, cryo-EM and X-ray crystallographic analyses on the replicative polymerase are used to identify the possible amino acids at the active sites of the plant replicative pol δ and their polymerase and PR functions.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. MSA Analysis of DNA Polymerase δ from Plant Sources

Figure 3 shows the MSA of DNA pols δ from various plant sources. (Only the required regions for the discussions are shown). The *A. thaliana* sequence is used as the standard and highlighted. The N-terminal region (~ 300 amino acids) shows small and large gaps in the alignment (data not shown), which is followed by the highly conserved PR exonuclease domain. The PR exonuclease domain contains the typical and completely conserved active site amino acids (highlighted in light blue) as reported in other PR DNA pols. The PR exonuclease domain is followed by the pol domain which is also highly conserved in all. The completely conserved pol active site amino acids are highlighted in yellow. The characteristic -SLYPS- and -YGD TDS- motifs of δ pol are found before and after the proposed pol active site, respectively, and their possible functions are discussed elsewhere. A polybasic, highly conserved, hexapeptide (highlighted in light violet) is found between them. Dx D types of metal-binding motifs are also observed in the PR and polymerase domains. The C-terminal region shows only a few gaps and consists of the three important regulatory motifs, viz. a PCNA interacting peptide (PIP), a ZBM and a Fe-S-ZBM, which are found to be very similar to animal δ pols [6]. Interestingly, all the three eukaryotic replicative DNA pols (pol α , ϵ and δ) contain two such conserved Cys-rich metal-binding motifs in their C-terminal domains of their catalytic subunits and are named CysA and CysB. The CysA is the regular ZBM whereas in the CysB motif, a Zn^{2+} binds to a 4Fe-4S cluster [15]. The PIP is highlighted in light magenta and its role in replication is discussed elsewhere. It is interesting to note that all δ pols invariably end in an aromatic amino acid, F/W/Y (highlighted) as in animal δ pol. The ζ pol, an error-prone polymerase specialized in translesion DNA synthesis, which is also classified under B-family pols, possesses similar catalytic core amino acids (-²⁷¹⁹RQ-⁴LGLK¹LIANVTF⁸GYT-) and the characteristic -²⁶¹⁶SYLPS- and -²⁷⁷⁸YGDTS- motifs suggesting not only that the δ pols could also perform translesion synthesis, but also their common origin of evolution.

CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) MSA of the δ polymerases from various plant sources.

tr U5H8M8 U5H8M8_USTV1	RNDN---DDDKNVNFESILKGLNEEVATDSSDQK	↑ PR Exo →	WNRPALPP--IDPDTDALIFQQIELEE	140
tr C1E609 C1E609_MICCC	HPSDPRI PDGVFPARAPRRSQVNVANDAEREH		WKRKPAPT--LDASKDNLCFQQQLDIDY	135
tr Q33BV0 Q33BV0_AUXPY	-----EVDEGTLGEAGKN		WPRPPPPQ--LNPASTSLVFQQLEVDY	88
sp Q9LVN7 DPOD1_ARATH	-----LIL-----RDIEERE---SRSSA		WARPPLSPAYLS-NSQSIIFQQLEIDS	104
tr A0A3P6BBX0 A0A3P6BBX0_BRAOL	-----LIL-----RDMEEREALSARSST		WARPPLSPAYLA-NSQSIIFQQLEIDY	99
tr A0A397Z0B4 A0A397Z0B4_BRACM	-----LIL-----RDMEEREALSARSST		WARPPLSPAYLA-NSQSIIFQQLEIDY	99
tr A0A078I2E2 A0A078I2E2_BRANA	-----LIL-----RDMEEREALSARSST		WARPPLSPAYLA-NSQSIIFQQLEIDY	99
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	-----LLL-----DRDEALASRLSR		WKRPALPADLVSGCSRSVAFQQQLDIDY	130
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	-----LLL-----DRDEALASRLSR		WKRPALPADLVSGCSRSVAFQQQLDIDY	110
tr A0A453HJ27 A0A453HJ27_AEGTS	-----LLL-----DRDEALASRLSR		WKRPALPADLVSGCSRSVAFQQQLDIDY	125
tr A0A6G1C319 A0A6G1C319_9ORYZ	-----LLL-----DRDEALASRLSR		WKRPALPADLVSGCSRSVAFQQQLDIDY	114
sp Q9LRE6 DPOD1_ORYSJ	-----LLL-----DRDEALASRLSR		WRRPALPADLVSGCSRSVAFQQLEIDY	112
tr A0A0E0MDA8 A0A0E0MDA8_ORYPU	-----LLL-----DRDEALASRLSR		WKRPALPADLVSGCSRSVAFQQLEIDY	114
tr A0A5J9USA3 A0A5J9USA3_9POAL	-----QLL-----QRDEALASRLSR		WKRPPPADLVAGCSRAVAFQQLEIDY	107
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	-----LML-----QRDEALASRLSR		WKRPAIPTDLAAGCSRTVAFQQLEIDY	110
tr A0A2S3ICY2 A0A2S3ICY2_9POAL	-----LML-----QRDEALASRLSR		WKRPALPADLVAGCSRSVAFQQLEIDY	110
tr K3ZGZ6 K3ZGZ6_SETIT	-----LMI-----QRDEALASRLSR		WKRPPPADLVAGCSRTVAFQQLEIDY	112
tr A0A2P2KVG9 A0A2P2KVG9_RHIMU	-----VRRQVLASRLAK		WRRPPLSGAYLS-QSQSITFQQLEMDY	98
tr A0A0S3RFB6 A0A0S3RFB6_PHAAN	-----ILR-----D-IEQRHALAARLSK		WTRPPLSDDYVA-QSRGVVVFQQLEIDY	93
tr A0A7J7DZR4 A0A7J7DZR4_TRIWF	-----ILR-----D-IEEREAIVARLAR		WARPALSDDYLS-QAKNIFLQQLEMDY	94
tr A0A200Q8R4 A0A200Q8R4_9MAGN	-----LIQ-----DEEDRRQLLASRLSK		WKRPTSSPCN-----LITRIDY	60
tr A0A2P6RSP9 A0A2P6RSP9_ROSCH	-----ILR-----D-SEGRQSLASRLTR		WARPPLSDAYKS-ASKSILFQQLEIDY	98
tr A0A2I4F7Z3 A0A2I4F7Z3_JUGRE	-----ILR-----D-SEGQALAAARLSK		WSRPPLSDAYVS-QRSRILFQQLEIDY	94
tr A0A6J5U1U4 A0A6J5U1U4_PRUAR	-----ILR-----D-IEERQSLASRLTK		WARPSISHAYSS-ASRSIAFQQLEIDY	94
tr A0A5E4GBB6 A0A5E4GBB6_PRUDU	-----ILR-----D-IEERQSLASRLTK		WARPSISHAYSS-ASRSIAFQQLEIDY	94
tr A0A6P5S1M3 A0A6P5S1M3_PRUAV	-----ILR-----D-IEERQALASRLTK		WARPSISHAYIS-ASRSIAFQQLEIDY	94
			* * * * * :	

tr U5H8M8 U5H8M8_USTV1	YLPQRIMDKLMCFINYIEMARVTGIPFNYSLLSRGQIKVISQLFRKAQDNTNLY	PR Exo	PAFRSE	596
tr C1E609 C1E609_MICCC	YLPQRLLDKLMYMYNYIEMARVTGVPLSFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQGLLV		PHIAKK	613
tr Q33BV0 Q33BV0_AUXFY	YLPQRLLVDKLMIMYNYIEMARVTGVPMPSYLLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKBRTKGLVV		PNNKRG	560
sp Q9LVN7 DPOD1_ARATH	YLPQRLLDKLMFIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKGQKQNLVL		PNAKQS	572
tr A0A3P6BBX0 A0A3P6BBX0_BRAOL	YLPQRLLDKLMCIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNMVL		PNAKQS	567
tr A0A397Z0B4 A0A397Z0B4_BRACM	YLPQRLLDKLMCIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNMVL		PNAKQS	567
tr A0A078I2E2 A0A078I2E2_BRANA	YLPQRLLDKLMCIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNMVL		PNAKQS	567
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	YLPQRLLDKLMYIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PNIKGQ	598
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	YLPQRLLDKLMYIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PNIKGQ	578
tr A0A453HJ27 A0A453HJ27_AEGTS	YLPQRLLDKLMYIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PNIKGQ	593
tr A0A6G1C319 A0A6G1C319_9ORYZ	YLPQRLLDKLMYIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PNIKGQ	564
sp Q9LRE6 DPOD1_ORYSJ	YLPQRLLDKLMYIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PNIKGQ	580
tr A0A0E0MDA8 A0A0E0MDA8_ORYPU	YLPQRLLDKLMYIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PNIKGQ	564
tr A0A5J9USA3 A0A5J9USA3_9POAL	YLPQRLLDKLMYIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PNIKGQ	575
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	YLPQRLLDKLMYIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PNIKGQ	578
tr A0A2S3ICY2 A0A2S3ICY2_9POAL	YLPQRLLDKLMYIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PNIKGQ	578
tr K3ZGZ6 K3ZGZ6_SETIT	YLPQRLLDKLMYIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PNIKGQ	580
tr A0A2P2KVG9 A0A2P2KVG9_RHIMU	YLPQRLLDKLMFIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKGLVI		PNVKQA	567
tr A0A0S3RFB6 A0A0S3RFB6_PHAAN	YLPQRLLDKLMFIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PNVKQV	561
tr A0A7J7DZR4 A0A7J7DZR4_TRIWF	YLPQRLLDKLMYIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PNVKQA	562
tr A0A200Q8R4 A0A200Q8R4_9MAGN	YLPQRLLDKLMYIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PSVRKQ	528
tr A0A2P6RSP9 A0A2P6RSP9_ROSCH	YLPQRLLDKLMFIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PNVKQA	565
tr A0A2I4F7Z3 A0A2I4F7Z3_JUGRE	YLPQRLLDKLMFIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKGLVI		PNVKHA	562
tr A0A6J5U1U4 A0A6J5U1U4_PRUAR	YLPQRLLDKLMYIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PNVKQA	561
tr A0A5E4GBB6 A0A5E4GBB6_PRUDU	YLPQRLLDKLMYIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PNVKQA	561
tr A0A6P5S1M3 A0A6P5S1M3_PRUAV	YLPQRLLDKLMYIYNYVEMARVTGVPI SFLLRGQSIKVLSQLRKAQKQNLVI		PNVKQA	561

tr U5H8M8 U5H8M8_USTV1	GS-----DEQYEGATVIEPEKGYVDVPIATLDFASLYPS	IMQAHNLCYTTLLDAKIAEA	650
tr C1E609 C1E609_MICCC	GGGEQADGGVAYEGATVLDKAGYYEMPVATLDFASLYPS	IMMAHNLCTSLVPRDRV--	671
tr Q33BV0 Q33BV0_AUXFY	GD---AGEGVAYEGATVLEPRAGYDPRVATLDFASLYPS	IMMAHNLCTTLLPKGQ---	615
sp Q9LVN7 DPOD1_ARATH	GS-----EQGTYEGATVLEARTGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVTPEDVRK	627
tr A0A3P6BBX0 A0A3P6BBX0_BRAOL	GS-----EQGTFEAGATVLEARTGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVTPEDVRK	622
tr A0A397Z0B4 A0A397Z0B4_BRACM	GS-----EQGTFEAGATVLEARTGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVTPEDVRK	622
tr A0A078I2E2 A0A078I2E2_BRANA	GS-----EQGTFEAGATVLEARTGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVTPEDVRK	622
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	SS-----GQDTFEAGATVLEARAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAHNLCTLVPPEDVRK	653
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	SS-----GQDTFEAGATVLEARAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAHNLCTLVPPEDVRK	633
tr A0A453HJ27 A0A453HJ27_AEGTS	SS-----GQDTFEAGATVLEARAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAHNLCTLVPPEDVRK	648
tr A0A6G1C319 A0A6G1C319_9ORYZ	GS-----GQDTFEAGATVLEARAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPPEDVRK	619
sp Q9LRE6 DPOD1_ORYSJ	AS-----GQDTFEAGATVLEARAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPPEDARK	635
tr A0A0E0MDA8 A0A0E0MDA8_ORYPU	AS-----GQDTFEAGATVLEARAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPPEDARK	619
tr A0A5J9USA3 A0A5J9USA3_9POAL	GS-----GQDTFEAGATVLEARAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPPEDARK	630
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	GS-----GQDTFEAGATVLEARAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPPEDARK	633
tr A0A2S3ICY2 A0A2S3ICY2_9POAL	GS-----GQDTFEAGATVLEASAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPPEDARK	633
tr K3ZGZ6 K3ZGZ6_SETIT	GS-----GQDTFEAGATVLEARAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPPEDARK	635
tr A0A2P2KVG9 A0A2P2KVG9_RHIMU	GS-----EQGTYEGATVLEAKAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVTPEDVRK	622
tr A0A0S3RFB6 A0A0S3RFB6_PHAAN	GS-----EQGTFEAGATVLEARAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVTPEDVRK	616
tr A0A7J7DZR4 A0A7J7DZR4_TRIWF	GS-----EQGTYEGATVLEAKAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVTPEDVRK	617
tr A0A200Q8R4 A0A200Q8R4_9MAGN	GS-----GEGTFEAGATVLEARTGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVTPEDVRK	583
tr A0A2P6RSP9 A0A2P6RSP9_ROSCH	GS-----EQGTYEGATVLEAKAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVRSSEVRK	620
tr A0A2I4F7Z3 A0A2I4F7Z3_JUGRE	GS-----EQGTYEGATVLEARAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVTPEDVRK	617
tr A0A6J5U1U4 A0A6J5U1U4_PRUAR	GS-----EQGTYEGATVLEAKAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVTPEDVRK	616
tr A0A5E4GBB6 A0A5E4GBB6_PRUDU	GS-----EQGTYEGATVLEAKAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVTPEDVRK	616
tr A0A6P5S1M3 A0A6P5S1M3_PRUAV	GS-----EQGTYEGATVLEAKAGFYEKPIATLDFASLYPS	IMMAYNLCYCTLVTPEDVRK	616

tr U5H8M8 U5H8M8_USTV1	LNLKEGVYVTRPNNDLFVKSEKRGLLPIILEDLLSARKRARAELKKETDFFKRAVLGD	710
tr C1E609 C1E609_MICCC	QFMAS-EDVTRTPCGDFTVFKSHKKGILPEILTELLSARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	730
tr Q33BV0 Q33BV0_AUXFY	KMFPS-EHLTFPNNDFVFKPSLQKQILPEILEELITARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	674
sp Q9LVN7 DPOD1_ARATH	LNLPP-EHVTKTPSGETFFVKQTLQKQILPEILEELITARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	686
tr A0A3P6BBX0 A0A3P6BBX0_BRAOL	LNLPP-EHINKTPSGETFFVKQTLQKQILPEILEELITARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	681
tr A0A397Z0B4 A0A397Z0B4_BRACM	LNLPP-EHINKTPSGETFFVKQTLQKQILPEILEELITARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	681
tr A0A078I2E2 A0A078I2E2_BRANA	LNLPP-EHINKTPSGETFFVKQTLQKQILPEILEELITARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	681
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	LNLPP-ESLYKTPSGEIFVKPELQKQILPEILEELLAARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	712
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	LNLPP-ESLYKTPSGEIFVKPELQKQILPEILEELLAARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	692
tr A0A453HJ27 A0A453HJ27_AEGTS	LNLPP-ESLYKTPSGEIFVKPELQKQILPEILEELLAARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	707
tr A0A6G1C319 A0A6G1C319_9ORYZ	LNLPP-ESLNKTPSGETFFVKPELQKQILPEILEELLAARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	678
sp Q9LRE6 DPOD1_ORYSJ	LNLPP-ESVNTTPSGETFFVKPDVQKQILPEILEELLAARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	694
tr A0A0E0MDA8 A0A0E0MDA8_ORYPU	LNLPP-ESVNTTPSGETFFVKPEVQKQILPEILEELLAARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	678
tr A0A5J9USA3 A0A5J9USA3_9POAL	LNLPP-ESLNRTPSGEIFVKPELQKQILPEILEELLAARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	689
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	LNLPP-EFVNTTPSGEIFVKPELQKQILPEILEELLAARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	692
tr A0A2S3ICY2 A0A2S3ICY2_9POAL	LNLPP-ESLNKTPSGEIFVKPDQKQILPEILEELLAARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	692
tr K3ZGZ6 K3ZGZ6_SETIT	LNLPP-ESLNKTPSGEIFVKPELQKQILPEILEELLAARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	694
tr A0A2P2KVG9 A0A2P2KVG9_RHIMU	LNLPP-ECVNTTPSGETFFVKSTLQKQILPEILEELITARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	681
tr A0A0S3RFB6 A0A0S3RFB6_PHAAN	LNIPI-ESLNKTPSGETFFVKSNTLQKQILPEILEELITARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	675
tr A0A7J7DZR4 A0A7J7DZR4_TRIWF	LNLPP-ECVNTTPSGEMFVKPNLQKQILPEILEELITARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	676
tr A0A200Q8R4 A0A200Q8R4_9MAGN	LNLPP-ECVNTTPSGETFFVKSNTLQKQILPEILEELLAARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	642
tr A0A2P6RSP9 A0A2P6RSP9_ROSCH	LNLPP-ECVNTTPSGETFFVKNLQKQILPEILEELLAARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	679
tr A0A2I4F7Z3 A0A2I4F7Z3_JUGRE	LNLPP-ECVNTTPSGETFFIKSNLQKQILPEILEELITARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	676
tr A0A6J5U1U4 A0A6J5U1U4_PRUAR	LNIPI-EFVNTTPSGETFFVKSNTLQKQILPEILEELITARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	675
tr A0A5E4GBB6 A0A5E4GBB6_PRUDU	LNIPI-EFVNTTPSGETFFVKSNTLQKQILPEILEELLAARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	675
tr A0A6P5S1M3 A0A6P5S1M3_PRUAV	LNIPI-EFVNTTPSGETFFVKSNTLQKQILPEILEELLAARKRKAADLKEAKDPLEKAVLGD	675

tr U5H8M8 U5H8M8_USTV1	ROLALKVSANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	QI SMSVTAYGRQMIERTKQEVQDRYNTANGYEYD	770
tr C1E609 C1E609_MICCC	ROLALKVSANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSTTAFGREMIDHTKAMVEKRYTTANGYKAN	790
tr Q33BV0 Q33BV0_AUXPY	ROLALKVSANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSFGREMIMETRRRVQERYCKANGYSHD	734
sp Q9LVN7 DPOD1_ARATH	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYQYN	746
tr A0A3P6BBX0 A0A3P6BBX0_BRAOL	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	741
tr A0A397Z0B4 A0A397Z0B4_BRACM	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	741
tr A0A078I2E2 A0A078I2E2_BRANA	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	741
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	772
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	752
tr A0A453HJ27 A0A453HJ27_AEGTS	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	767
tr A0A6G1C319 A0A6G1C319_9ORYZ	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	738
sp Q9LRE6 DPOD1_ORYSJ	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	754
tr A0A0E0MDA8 A0A0E0MDA8_ORYPU	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	738
tr A0A5J9USA3 A0A5J9USA3_9POAL	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	749
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	752
tr A0A2S3ICY2 A0A2S3ICY2_9POAL	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	752
tr K3ZGZ6 K3ZGZ6_SETIT	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	754
tr A0A2P2KVG9 A0A2P2KVG9_RHIMU	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	741
tr A0A0S3RFB6 A0A0S3RFB6_PHAAN	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	735
tr A0A7J7DZR4 A0A7J7DZR4_TRIWF	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	736
tr A0A200Q8R4 A0A200Q8R4_9MAGN	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	702
tr A0A2P6RSP9 A0A2P6RSP9_ROSCH	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	739
tr A0A2I4F7Z3 A0A2I4F7Z3_JUGRE	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	736
tr A0A6J5U1U4 A0A6J5U1U4_PRUAR	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	735
tr A0A5E4GBB6 A0A5E4GBB6_PRUDU	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	735
tr A0A6P5S1M3 A0A6P5S1M3_PRUAV	ROLALKISANSVYFTGATVGLPCLEI	ISSSVTSYGRQMIETQKKLVDEKFTTLGGYEYN	735

tr U5H8M8 U5H8M8_USTV1	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	830
tr C1E609 C1E609_MICCC	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	850
tr Q33BV0 Q33BV0_AUXPY	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	794
sp Q9LVN7 DPOD1_ARATH	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLINKRR	806
tr A0A3P6BBX0 A0A3P6BBX0_BRAOL	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLINKRR	801
tr A0A397Z0B4 A0A397Z0B4_BRACM	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLINKRR	801
tr A0A078I2E2 A0A078I2E2_BRANA	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLINKRR	801
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLINKRR	832
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	812
tr A0A453HJ27 A0A453HJ27_AEGTS	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	827
tr A0A6G1C319 A0A6G1C319_9ORYZ	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	798
sp Q9LRE6 DPOD1_ORYSJ	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	814
tr A0A0E0MDA8 A0A0E0MDA8_ORYPU	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	798
tr A0A5J9USA3 A0A5J9USA3_9POAL	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	809
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	812
tr A0A2S3ICY2 A0A2S3ICY2_9POAL	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	812
tr K3ZGZ6 K3ZGZ6_SETIT	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	814
tr A0A2P2KVG9 A0A2P2KVG9_RHIMU	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	801
tr A0A0S3RFB6 A0A0S3RFB6_PHAAN	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	795
tr A0A7J7DZR4 A0A7J7DZR4_TRIWF	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	796
tr A0A200Q8R4 A0A200Q8R4_9MAGN	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	762
tr A0A2P6RSP9 A0A2P6RSP9_ROSCH	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	799
tr A0A2I4F7Z3 A0A2I4F7Z3_JUGRE	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	796
tr A0A6J5U1U4 A0A6J5U1U4_PRUAR	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	795
tr A0A5E4GBB6 A0A5E4GBB6_PRUDU	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	795
tr A0A6P5S1M3 A0A6P5S1M3_PRUAV	AEVLYGDTDSVMVQFVGVDDVAAAMQLGREAAEYISGTFIKPIKLEFEKVIYFPYLLISKRR	795

tr U5H8M8 U5H8M8_USTV1	YAGLWTKPEKYDKMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	890
tr C1E609 C1E609_MICCC	YAGLWTKPEKYDKMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	910
tr Q33BV0 Q33BV0_AUXPY	YAGLWTKPEKYDKMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	854
sp Q9LVN7 DPOD1_ARATH	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	866
tr A0A3P6BBX0 A0A3P6BBX0_BRAOL	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIA	861
tr A0A397Z0B4 A0A397Z0B4_BRACM	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIA	861
tr A0A078I2E2 A0A078I2E2_BRANA	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIA	861
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	892
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	872
tr A0A453HJ27 A0A453HJ27_AEGTS	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	887
tr A0A6G1C319 A0A6G1C319_9ORYZ	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	858
sp Q9LRE6 DPOD1_ORYSJ	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	874
tr A0A0E0MDA8 A0A0E0MDA8_ORYPU	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	858
tr A0A5J9USA3 A0A5J9USA3_9POAL	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	869
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	872
tr A0A2S3ICY2 A0A2S3ICY2_9POAL	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	872
tr K3ZGZ6 K3ZGZ6_SETIT	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	874
tr A0A2P2KVG9 A0A2P2KVG9_RHIMU	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	861
tr A0A0S3RFB6 A0A0S3RFB6_PHAAN	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	855
tr A0A7J7DZR4 A0A7J7DZR4_TRIWF	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	856
tr A0A200Q8R4 A0A200Q8R4_9MAGN	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	822
tr A0A2P6RSP9 A0A2P6RSP9_ROSCH	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	859
tr A0A2I4F7Z3 A0A2I4F7Z3_JUGRE	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIA	856
tr A0A6J5U1U4 A0A6J5U1U4_PRUAR	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	855
tr A0A5E4GBB6 A0A5E4GBB6_PRUDU	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	855
tr A0A6P5S1M3 A0A6P5S1M3_PRUAV	YAGLWLTNPQKFKDMDTKGIETVRRDNC	LLVKNLVTECLHKILVDRDPVGAEEYVKNTIS	855

Figure 3 MSA of the δ polymerase from various plant species

U5H8M8_USTV1 DNA polymerase, *Microbotryum lychnidis-dioicae* (an obligate biotrophic plant parasite)
 C1E609_MICCC DNA polymerase, *Micromonas commode* (a eukaryotic, photosynthetic microbe)
 Q33BV0_AUXPY DNA polymerase, *Auxenochlorella pyrenoidosa* (Chlorella)
Q9LVN7|DPOD1_ARATH DNA polymerase, *Arabidopsis thaliana*
 A0A3P6BBX0_BRAOL DNA polymerase, *Brassica oleracea*
 A0A397Z0B4_BRACM DNA polymerase, *Brassica campestris*
 A0A078I2E2_BRANA DNA polymerase, *Brassica napus*
 A0A287NEC0_HORVV DNA polymerase, *Hordeum vulgare subsp. Vulgare*
 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT DNA polymerase, *Triticum aestivum*
 A0A453HJ27_AEGTS DNA polymerase, *Aegilops tauschii subsp. Strangulate*
 A0A6G1C319_9ORYZ DNA polymerase, *Oryza meyeriana var. granulate*
 Q9LRE6|DPOD1_ORYSJ DNA polymerase, *Oryza sativa subsp. Japonica*
 A0A0E0MDA8_ORYPU DNA polymerase, *Oryza punctate*
 A0A5J9USA3_9POAL DNA polymerase, *Eragrostis curvula*
 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE DNA polymerase, *Zea mays*
 A0A2S3ICY2_9POAL DNA polymerase, *Panicum hallii*
 K3ZGZ6_SETIT DNA polymerase, *Setaria italic*
 A0A2P2KVG9_RHIMU DNA polymerase, *Rhizophora mucronata*
 A0A0S3RFB6_PHAAN DNA polymerase, *Vigna angularis var. angularis*
 A0A7J7DZR4_TRIWF DNA polymerase, *Tripterygium wilfordii*
 A0A200Q8R4_9MAGN DNA polymerase, *Macleaya cordata*
 A0A2P6RSP9_ROSCH DNA polymerase, *Rosa chinensis*
 A0A2I4F7Z3_JUGRE DNA polymerase, *Juglans regia*
 A0A6J5U1U4_PRUAR DNA polymerase, *Prunus armeniaca*
 A0A5E4GBB6_PRUDU DNA polymerase, *Prunus dulcis*
 A0A6P5S1M3_PRUAV DNA polymerase, *Prunus avium*

Figure 4 shows the 'Mix and Match' MSA of the plant and animal δ pols (only the required regions for the discussions are shown). The plant sequences are highlighted in green and the animal sequences in black. There are large and small gaps in the N-terminal domains (data not shown). The PR exonuclease domain shows many conservations in both δ pols, but much higher conservations are observed at the end of the PR domain. It is interesting to note that the PR exonuclease active site amino acids (highlighted in light blue) are completely conserved in both plant and animal δ pols (Fig. 4). However, the second domain, i.e., the pol domain is highly conserved throughout. The polymerase active site amino acids are also completely conserved in both the δ pols (highlighted in yellow). The -DxD- metal-binding motifs are highly conserved in both and highlighted in dark green. The characteristic motifs found in the δ pols, viz. -SYLPS- and YGDTD- are completely conserved in both δ pols and their significance is discussed elsewhere. The highly conserved polybasic peptide is found in both pols and placed in between them (highlighted in light violet). However, the larger conserved peptide carrying the -SYLPS- motif shows marked differences in four amino acids, -FYEKPIATLDFASLYPS- (from plant sources, *A. thaliana*) and -YYDVPIATLDFSSLYPS- (from animal sources, humans). However, the BLASTp analysis has shown only 56.57% identity between the plant (*A. thaliana*) and animal (human) δ pols. The pI values of *A. thaliana* and human δ pols showed a marked difference, 8.00 and 6.64, respectively. Apart from the conserved Cs of the ZBMs in the CTD, there are other completely conserved C residues in both pols (highlighted in orange) which could possibly play a role in disulphide bond formation. The PIP heptapeptide is found in both the δ pols in the CTD and is highlighted in magenta. Even though the PIPs are conserved in both plants and animals, but small variations are observed between them as shown: -S/GGIMKFA- (from plant sources) and -GLLAFA- (from animal sources). Interestingly, both plant and animal δ pol sequences almost end in an aromatic amino acid (**F** in plants and **W** in animals). The significance of such similar endings in all δ pol sequences is not clear now.

CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) MSA of δ pols from animal and plant sources

		NTD ← NRS → EXO		
sp Q9LVN7 DP0D1_ARATH	-----LILRDIEERE--SRSSA		WARPPPLSPAYL--SNSQSIIFQOLEIDSIIAESHK	111
tr AOA3P6BBX0 AOA3P6BBX0_BRAOL	-----LILRDMEEREALSARSSST		WARPPPLSPAYL--ANSQSIIFQOLEIDYVIKEIKH	106
tr AOA397Z0B4 AOA397Z0B4_BRACM	-----LILRDMEREALSARSSST		WARPPPLSPAYL--ANSQSIIFQOLEIDYVIKEIKH	106
tr AOA153A927 AOA153A927_BRANA	-----LILRDMEREALSARSSST		WARPPPLPADLVSGCSRSRVAFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	117
tr AOA3B6JHK9 AOA3B6JHK9_WHEAT	-----LLL--DRDEALASLRSLR		WKRPPALPADLVSGCSRSRVAFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	117
tr AOA287NEC0 AOA287NEC0_HORVV	-----LLL--DRDEALASLRSLR		WKRPPALPADLVSGCSRSRVAFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	137
tr AOA661C319 AOA661C319_9ORYZ	-----LLL--DRDEALASLRSLR		WKRPPALPADLVSGCSRSRVAFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	121
sp Q9LRE6 DP0D1_ORYS7	-----LLL--DRDEALASLRSLR		WKRPPALPADLVSGCSRSRVAFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	119
tr AOA0E0MDA8 AOA0E0MDA8_ORYPU	-----LLL--DRDEALASLRSLR		WKRPPALPADLVSGCSRSRVAFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	121
tr AOA5J9USA3 AOA5J9USA3_9POAL	-----QLL--QRDEALASLRSLR		WKRPPALPADLVGCSRAVAFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	114
tr AOA1D6QLT8 AOA1D6QLT8_MAIZE	-----LML--QRDEALASLRSLR		WKRPPALPADLVGCSRAVAFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	109
tr AOA2S3ICY2 AOA2S3ICY2_9POAL	-----LMI--QRDEALASLRSLR		WKRPPALPADLVGCSRSRVAFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	117
tr K3ZGZ6 K3ZGZ6_SEITIT	-----LMI--QRDEALASLRSLR		WKRPPALPADLVGCSRSRVAFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	119
tr AOA2P2KVG9 AOA2P2KVG9_RHIMU	-----VREQVVASLRSLR		WKRPPALSGAYL--SQSQSITFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	105
tr AOA7J7DZR4 AOA7J7DZR4_TRIFW	-----ILRD--IEEREAIVASLRSLR		WARPPALSDYL--SQAKNITFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	101
tr AOA200QBR4 AOA200QBR4_9MAGN	-----LLODEEDRQLASLRSLR		WKRPPALSDYL--SQAKNITFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	67
tr AOA2P6RSP9 AOA2P6RSP9_ROSCH	-----ILRD--SEQRQASLRSLR		WKRPPALSDYL--SQAKNITFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	105
tr AOA214F7Z3 AOA214F7Z3_JUGRE	-----ILRD--SEGRQALASLRSLR		WKRPPALSDYL--SQAKNITFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	101
tr AOA63JUL4 AOA63JUL4_PRUAR	-----ILRD--IEERQASLRSLR		WARPPALSDYL--SQAKNITFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	101
tr AOA5E4GBB6 AOA5E4GBB6_PRUDU	-----ILRD--IEERQASLRSLR		WARPPALSDYL--SQAKNITFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	101
tr AOA6P5S1M3 AOA6P5S1M3_PRUAV	-----ILRD--IEERQASLRSLR		WARPPALSDYL--SQAKNITFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	101
tr AOA6F5I296 AOA6F5I296_PHACI	EEEEELH-LPP--EGAEGHTFSAWTDPR		WLRPAPPAL--DPKQALVQOLEIDYVIGESHK	146
sp P52431 DP0D1_MOUSE	EEEEELQ--PPEGIVGGQFSTADIDPR		WRRPPLRAL--DPSTELIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	107
sp O54747 DP0D1_RAT	EEEEELQ--PPEGIVGGQFSTADIDPR		WLRPPLRAL--DPSTELIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	105
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	EEEEELQ--PPEGIVGGQFSTADIDPR		WLRPPLRAL--DPSTELIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	105
tr AOA1S3A927 AOA1S3A927_ERIEU	EEE--ALQVLEAVDGGQSSAIDPR		WLRPPLRAL--DPSTELIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	107
tr HOV251 HOV251_CAVPO	EEE--ELQSAQAADGGQSSAIDPR		WLRPPLRAL--DPSTELIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	107
tr AOA619JZ04 AOA619JZ04_CHRAS	EEE--ELQSAQAADGGQSSAIDPR		WLRPPLRAL--DPSTELIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	110
tr AOA7J7SK29 AOA7J7SK29_RHIFE	EEE--ELQSAQAADGGQSSAIDPR		WLRPPLRAL--DPSTELIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	112
sp P28340 DP0D1_HUMAN	EEE--ELQSVLEGVADGGVPSAIDPR		WLRPPLRAL--DPSTELIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	109
tr AOA2K6DGG8 AOA2K6DGG8_MACNE	EEE--ELQSVLEGVADGGVPSAIDPR		WLRPPLRAL--DPSTELIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	109
tr AOA0A0MW23 AOA0A0MW23_PAPAN	EEE--ELQSALEGA--DGGQSSAIDPR		WLRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	108
tr AOA6P7EPG1 AOA6P7EPG1_SHEEP	EEE--ELQSALEGA--DGGQSSAIDPR		WLRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	108
sp P28339 DP0D1_BOVIN	EEE--ELQSALEGA--DGGQSSAIDPR		WLRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	108
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	EEE--ELQSALEGA--DGGQSSAIDPR		WLRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	108
tr AOA383ZY66 AOA383ZY66_BALAS	EEE--ELQSALEGAADGGQSSAIDPR		WLRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	109
tr AOA2Y9P989 AOA2Y9P989_DELLE	EEE--ELQSALEGAADGGQSSAIDPR		WLRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	109
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	EEE--ELQSALEGAADGGQSSAIDPR		WLRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	109
tr AOA5G2QET9 AOA5G2QET9_FIG	EEE--ELQSALEGAADGGQSSAIDPR		WLRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	109
tr AOA6J1XK42 AOA6J1XK42_ACTIJB	EEE--LQPALEGADGGQSSAIDPR		WLRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	109
tr M3VUJ4 M3VUJ4_FELCA	EEE--LQPALEGADGGQSSAIDPR		WLRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	109
tr E2R5W5 E2R5W5_CANLF	EEE--LQPALEGADGGQSSAIDPR		WLRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	109
tr G1M3J7 G1M3J7_AILME	EEE--LQPALEGADGGQSSAIDPR		WLRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	109
tr AOA2U3ZRE1 AOA2U3ZRE1_ODORO	EQGAGHDVIP---VGDLFSA--DINPR		WRRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	109
tr AOA6J2WZ66 AOA6J2WZ66_CHACN	EQGAGHDVIP---VGDLFSA--DINPR		WRRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	103
tr Q2KNE0 Q2KNE0_DANRE	EQGAGHDVIP---VGDLFSA--DINPR		WRRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	103
tr AOA6P6JVN6 AOA6P6JVN6_CARAU	EQGAGHDVIP---VGDLFSA--DINPR		WRRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	103
tr AOA6P6JG77 AOA6P6JG77_CARAU	EQGAGHDVIP---VGDLFSA--DINPR		WRRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	103
tr AOA673JFI3 AOA673JFI3_9TELE	EQGAGHDVIP---VGDLFSA--DINPR		WRRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	103
tr AOA498LX53 AOA498LX53_LABRO	EQGAGHDVIP---VGDLFSA--DINPR		WRRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	103
tr COHA77 COHA77_SALSA	EQGAGHDVIP---VGDLFSA--DINPR		WRRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	103
tr AOA6P7IUM6 AOA6P7IUM6_9TELE	EQGAGHDVIP---VGDLFSA--DINPR		WRRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	102
tr AOA3Q3E049 AOA3Q3E049_HIPCM	EQGAGHDVIP---VGDLFSA--DINPR		WRRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	103
tr AOA4W3I8L4 AOA4W3I8L4_CALMI	EQGAGHDVIP---VGDLFSA--DINPR		WRRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	104
tr DOVEW7 DOVEW7_XENLA	EQGAGHDVIP---VGDLFSA--DINPR		WRRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	104
tr AOA6J1U352 AOA6J1U352_9SAUR	EAQLSSDAIP---LGNLFSS--IHNP		WRRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	108
tr AOA619XX64 AOA619XX64_9SAUR	EAQLSSDAIP---LGNLFSS--IHNP		WRRPAPPAL--DPQMEPLIFQOLEIDYVIGESHK	109

sp Q9LVN7 DP0D1_ARATH	-----RTLSYCOLEFHCLYSDLISHAAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	328
tr AOA3P6BBX0 AOA3P6BBX0_BRAOL	-----RTSSYCOLEFHCLYSDLISHAAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	323
tr AOA397Z0B4 AOA397Z0B4_BRACM	-----RTLSYCOLEFHCLYSDLISHAAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	323
tr AOA078I2E2 AOA078I2E2_BRANA	-----RTLSYCOLEFHCLYSDLISHAAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	323
tr AOA3B6JHK9 AOA3B6JHK9_WHEAT	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	334
tr AOA287NEC0 AOA287NEC0_HORVV	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	354
tr AOA661C319 AOA661C319_9ORYZ	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	320
sp Q9LRE6 DP0D1_ORYS7	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	320
tr AOA0E0MDA8 AOA0E0MDA8_ORYPU	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	320
tr AOA5J9USA3 AOA5J9USA3_9POAL	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	331
tr AOA1D6QLT8 AOA1D6QLT8_MAIZE	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	334
tr AOA2S3ICY2 AOA2S3ICY2_9POAL	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	334
tr K3ZGZ6 K3ZGZ6_SEITIT	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	336
tr AOA2P2KVG9 AOA2P2KVG9_RHIMU	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	323
tr AOA7J7DZR4 AOA7J7DZR4_TRIFW	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	318
tr AOA200QBR4 AOA200QBR4_9MAGN	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	284
tr AOA2P6RSP9 AOA2P6RSP9_ROSCH	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	321
tr AOA214F7Z3 AOA214F7Z3_JUGRE	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	318
tr AOA63JUL4 AOA63JUL4_PRUAR	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	317
tr AOA5E4GBB6 AOA5E4GBB6_PRUDU	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	317
tr AOA6P5S1M3 AOA6P5S1M3_PRUAV	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	317
tr AOA6F5I296 AOA6F5I296_PHACI	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	366
sp P52431 DP0D1_MOUSE	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	330
sp O54747 DP0D1_RAT	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	328
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	328
tr AOA1S3A927 AOA1S3A927_ERIEU	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	332
tr HOV251 HOV251_CAVPO	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	332
tr AOA619JZ04 AOA619JZ04_CHRAS	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	334
tr AOA7J7SK29 AOA7J7SK29_RHIFE	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	340
sp P28340 DP0D1_HUMAN	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	332
tr AOA2K6DGG8 AOA2K6DGG8_MACNE	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	332
tr AOA0A0MW23 AOA0A0MW23_PAPAN	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	332
tr AOA452F6S3 AOA452F6S3_CAPHI	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	331
tr AOA6P7EPG1 AOA6P7EPG1_SHEEP	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	331
sp P28339 DP0D1_BOVIN	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	331
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	331
tr AOA383ZY66 AOA383ZY66_BALAS	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	332
tr AOA2Y9P989 AOA2Y9P989_DELLE	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	332
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	332
tr AOA5G2QET9 AOA5G2QET9_FIG	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	332
tr AOA6J1XK42 AOA6J1XK42_ACTIJB	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	332
tr M3VUJ4 M3VUJ4_FELCA	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	332
tr E2R5W5 E2R5W5_CANLF	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	332
tr G1M3J7 G1M3J7_AILME	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	332
tr AOA2U3ZRE1 AOA2U3ZRE1_ODORO	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	332
tr AOA6J2WZ66 AOA6J2WZ66_CHACN	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	336
tr Q2KNE0 Q2KNE0_DANRE	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	336
tr AOA6P6JVN6 AOA6P6JVN6_CARAU	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	336
tr AOA6P6JG77 AOA6P6JG77_CARAU	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	336
tr AOA673JFI3 AOA673JFI3_9TELE	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	331
tr AOA498LX53 AOA498LX53_LABRO	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	336
tr COHA77 COHA77_SALSA	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	336
tr AOA6P7IUM6 AOA6P7IUM6_9TELE	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	335
tr AOA3Q3E049 AOA3Q3E049_HIPCM	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	336
tr AOA4W3I8L4 AOA4W3I8L4_CALMI	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	338
tr DOVEW7 DOVEW7_XENLA	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	336
tr AOA6J1U352 AOA6J1U352_9SAUR	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	339
tr AOA619XX64 AOA619XX64_9SAUR	-----RVMSYCOLELDCLYSDLVSHAPGEYSKMAFFRVLSEDIICA	---	GRKGHFFPEAKHD	342

Table with columns: sp|, accession numbers, protein names, and alignment scores. Includes entries for Q91LVN7|DPOD1_ARATH and P28340|DPOD1_HUMAN.

Table with columns: sp|, accession numbers, protein names, and alignment scores. Includes entries for Q91LVN7|DPOD1_ARATH and P28340|DPOD1_HUMAN, with a color-coded alignment bar at the bottom.

sp Q9LVN7 DP0D1_ARATH	NAKQSGSEQGTTEGATVLEARTG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	607
tr A0A3P6BBX0 A0A3P6BBX0_BRAOL	NAKQSGSEQGTTEGATVLEARTG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	602
tr A0A397Z0B4 A0A397Z0B4_BRACM	NAKQSGSEQGTTEGATVLEARTG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	602
tr A0A0781Z2E A0A0781Z2E_BRANA	NAKQSGSEQGTTEGATVLEARTG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	602
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	NIKQSSGQDTTEGATVLEARAG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	613
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	NIKQSSGQDTTEGATVLEARAG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	633
tr A0A6G1C319 A0A6G1C319_9ORYZ	NIKQSSGQDTTEGATVLEARAG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	599
sp Q9LRE6 DP0D1_ORYSJ	NIKQSSGQDTTEGATVLEARAG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	615
tr A0A0E0MDA8 A0A0E0MDA8_ORYPU	NIKQSSGQDTTEGATVLEARAG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	599
tr A0A5J9USA3 A0A5J9USA3_9POAL	NIKQSSGQDTTEGATVLEARAG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	610
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	NIKQSSGQDTTEGATVLEASAG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	613
tr A0A2S3ICY2 A0A2S3ICY2_9POAL	NIKQSSGQDTTEGATVLEARAG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	613
tr K3ZGZ6 K3ZGZ6_SETIT	NIKQSSGQDTTEGATVLEARAG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	615
tr A0A2P2KVG9 A0A2P2KVG9_RHIMU	NVKQAGSEQGTTEGATVLEAKAG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	602
tr A0A7J7DZR4 A0A7J7DZR4_TRIWF	NVKQAGSEQGTTEGATVLEAKAG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	597
tr A0A200Q8R4 A0A200Q8R4_9MAGN	SVRKQSGEGTTEGATVLEARTG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	563
tr A0A2P6RSP9 A0A2P6RSP9_ROSCH	NVKQAGSEQGTTEGATVLEAKAG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	600
tr A0A2I4F7Z3 A0A2I4F7Z3_JUGRE	NVKHAGSEQGTTEGATVLEARAG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	597
tr A0A6J5U1U4 A0A6J5U1U4_PRUAR	NVKQAGSEQGTTEGATVLEAKAG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	596
tr A0A5E4GBB6 A0A5E4GBB6_PRUDU	NVKQAGSEQGTTEGATVLEAKAG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	596
tr A0A6P5S1M3 A0A6P5S1M3_PRUAV	NVKQAGSEQGTTEGATVLEAKAG-----FYEKPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	596
tr A0A6P5I296 A0A6P5I296_PHACI	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	643
sp P52431 DP0D1_MOUSE	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	607
sp O54747 DP0D1_RAT	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	605
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	605
tr A0A1S3A927 A0A1S3A927_ERIEU	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	609
tr H0V251 H0V251_CAVEO	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	607
tr A0A6I9JZ04 A0A6I9JZ04_CHRAS	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	611
tr A0A7J7SK29 A0A7J7SK29_RHIFE	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	630
sp P28340 DP0D1_HUMAN	VVKSEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	609
tr A0A2K6D6G8 A0A2K6D6G8_MACNE	VVRSEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLKGLGAVCTSW--TPRRGAPCRYVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	626
tr A0A0A0MW23 A0A0A0MW23_PAPAN	VVRSEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	609
tr A0A452F6S3 A0A452F6S3_CAPHI	HTWVFP--SFFPGAAD--ARGEDDGT-----AEGAGQGYVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	617
tr A0A6P7EPG1 A0A6P7EPG1_SHEEP	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	608
sp P28339 DP0D1_BOVIN	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	608
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	608
tr A0A383ZY66 A0A383ZY66_BALAS	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	609
tr A0A2Y9P989 A0A2Y9P989_DELLE	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	609
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	609
tr A0A5G2QET9 A0A5G2QET9_PIG	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLKGLDGAAGVAVGLPVLTPPRTARYVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	629
tr A0A6J1XK42 A0A6J1XK42_ACIBJ	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	609
tr M3VUJ4 M3VUJ4_FELCA	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	609
tr E2R5W5 E2R5W5_CANLF	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	609
tr G1M3J7 G1M3J7_AILME	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	609
tr A0A2U3ZRE1 A0A2U3ZRE1_ODORO	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	609
tr A0A6J2WZ6 A0A6J2WZ6_CHACN	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	613
tr Q2KNE0 Q2KNE0_DANRE	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	613
tr A0A6P6JVN6 A0A6P6JVN6_CARAU	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	613
tr A0A6P6JG77 A0A6P6JG77_CARAU	VVKTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	613
tr A0A673JFI3 A0A673JFI3_9TELE	VVRTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPEK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	613
tr A0A498LX53 A0A498LX53_LABRO	VVRTEGG--EDYTGATVIEPEK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	608
tr COHA77 COHA77_SALSA	VVKPEGG--EDYTGATVIEPEK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	613
tr A0A6P7IUM6 A0A6P7IUM6_9TELE	VVKSQGG--EDYTGATVIEPEK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	612
tr A0A3Q3E049 A0A3Q3E049_HIPCM	VVKSQGG--EDYTGATVIEPEK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	613
tr A0A4W3I8L4 A0A4W3I8L4_CALMI	IVLAI DA--IDYCPWKT--RPS-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	613
tr D0VEW7 D0VEW7_XENLA	VVRSEGG--EDYTGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	614
tr A0A6J1U352 A0A6J1U352_9SAUR	VVKTEGG--EDYAGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	616
tr A0A6I9XX64 A0A6I9XX64_9SAUR	VVKTEGG--EDYAGATVIEPLK-----YVDVPIATLDFAS	SLYPS	619
	..*:*:*:*:*	*****	
sp Q9LVN7 DP0D1_ARATH	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		667
tr A0A3P6BBX0 A0A3P6BBX0_BRAOL	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		662
tr A0A397Z0B4 A0A397Z0B4_BRACM	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		662
tr A0A0781Z2E A0A0781Z2E_BRANA	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		662
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	IMMAHNLCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		662
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	IMMAHNLCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		693
tr A0A6G1C319 A0A6G1C319_9ORYZ	IMMAHNLCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		673
sp Q9LRE6 DP0D1_ORYSJ	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		675
tr A0A0E0MDA8 A0A0E0MDA8_ORYPU	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		659
tr A0A5J9USA3 A0A5J9USA3_9POAL	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		670
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		673
tr A0A2S3ICY2 A0A2S3ICY2_9POAL	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		673
tr K3ZGZ6 K3ZGZ6_SETIT	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		675
tr A0A2P2KVG9 A0A2P2KVG9_RHIMU	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		662
tr A0A7J7DZR4 A0A7J7DZR4_TRIWF	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		657
tr A0A200Q8R4 A0A200Q8R4_9MAGN	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		623
tr A0A2P6RSP9 A0A2P6RSP9_ROSCH	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		660
tr A0A2I4F7Z3 A0A2I4F7Z3_JUGRE	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		660
tr A0A6J5U1U4 A0A6J5U1U4_PRUAR	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		656
tr A0A5E4GBB6 A0A5E4GBB6_PRUDU	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		656
tr A0A6P5S1M3 A0A6P5S1M3_PRUAV	IMMAYNLCYCTLVPEPDRKLNLPPEHVNKTPSGETFVKQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		656
tr A0A6P5I296 A0A6P5I296_PHACI	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		703
sp P52431 DP0D1_MOUSE	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		667
sp O54747 DP0D1_RAT	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		665
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		665
tr A0A1S3A927 A0A1S3A927_ERIEU	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		669
tr H0V251 H0V251_CAVEO	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		667
tr A0A6I9JZ04 A0A6I9JZ04_CHRAS	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		671
tr A0A7J7SK29 A0A7J7SK29_RHIFE	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		690
sp P28340 DP0D1_HUMAN	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		669
tr A0A2K6D6G8 A0A2K6D6G8_MACNE	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		686
tr A0A0A0MW23 A0A0A0MW23_PAPAN	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		669
tr A0A452F6S3 A0A452F6S3_CAPHI	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		677
tr A0A6P7EPG1 A0A6P7EPG1_SHEEP	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		668
sp P28339 DP0D1_BOVIN	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		668
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		668
tr A0A383ZY66 A0A383ZY66_BALAS	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		669
tr A0A2Y9P989 A0A2Y9P989_DELLE	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		667
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		669
tr A0A5G2QET9 A0A5G2QET9_PIG	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		689
tr A0A6J1XK42 A0A6J1XK42_ACIBJ	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		669
tr M3VUJ4 M3VUJ4_FELCA	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		669
tr E2R5W5 E2R5W5_CANLF	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		669
tr G1M3J7 G1M3J7_AILME	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		669
tr A0A2U3ZRE1 A0A2U3ZRE1_ODORO	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		669
tr A0A6J2WZ6 A0A6J2WZ6_CHACN	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		669
tr Q2KNE0 Q2KNE0_DANRE	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		673
tr A0A6P6JVN6 A0A6P6JVN6_CARAU	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		673
tr A0A6P6JG77 A0A6P6JG77_CARAU	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		673
tr A0A673JFI3 A0A673JFI3_9TELE	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		673
tr A0A498LX53 A0A498LX53_LABRO	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		668
tr COHA77 COHA77_SALSA	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		673
tr A0A6P7IUM6 A0A6P7IUM6_9TELE	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		673
tr A0A3Q3E049 A0A3Q3E049_HIPCM	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		673
tr A0A4W3I8L4 A0A4W3I8L4_CALMI	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		673
tr D0VEW7 D0VEW7_XENLA	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		674
tr A0A6J1U352 A0A6J1U352_9SAUR	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		676
tr A0A6I9XX64 A0A6I9XX64_9SAUR	IMMAHNLCTLLRPGAQAKLGLTDEDFIKPTGDEFVKTQTLQKGLIPEILEELLTARKR		679
	****:*	*****	

sp Q9LVN7 DP0D1_ARATH	KILIDRDVPGAENVKKTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKSAHGELAERMRRK	906
tr A0A3P6BBX0 A0A3P6BBX0_BRAOL	KILIDRDVQGAAYEVKNTIADLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKSAHGELAERMRRK	901
tr A0A39720B4 A0A39720B4_BRACM	KILIDRDVQGAAYEVKNTIADLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKSAHGELAERMRRK	901
tr A0A07812E2 A0A07812E2_BRANA	KILIDRDVQGAAYEVKNTIADLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKSAHGELAERMRRK	901
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	912
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	932
tr A0A6G1C319 A0A6G1C319_9ORYZ	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	898
sp Q9LRE6 DP0D1_ORYSJ	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	914
tr A0A0E0MDA8 A0A0E0MDA8_ORYPU	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	909
tr A0A5J9USA3 A0A5J9USA3_9POAL	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	912
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	912
tr A0A2S3ICY2 A0A2S3ICY2_9POAL	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	912
tr K3ZGZ6 K3ZGZ6_SEITIT	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	914
tr A0A2P2KVG9 A0A2P2KVG9_RHIMU	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	901
tr A0A7J7DZR4 A0A7J7DZR4_TRIWF	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	862
tr A0A200Q8R4 A0A200Q8R4_9MAGN	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	896
tr A0A2P6RSP9 A0A2P6RSP9_ROSCH	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	899
tr A0A2I4F7Z3 A0A2I4F7Z3_JUGRE	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	896
tr A0A6J5U1U4 A0A6J5U1U4_PRUAR	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	895
tr A0A5E4GBB6 A0A5E4GBB6_PRUUD	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	895
tr A0A6P5S1M3 A0A6P5S1M3_PRUAV	KILIDRDVPGAQVYKNTISDLLMNRDLSLLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKAAHVLAERMRRK	895
tr A0A6P5I296 A0A6P5I296_PHACI	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	943
sp P52431 DP0D1_MOUSE	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	907
tr O54747 DP0D1_RAT	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	905
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	905
tr A0A1S3A927 A0A1S3A927_ERIEU	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	909
tr H0V251 H0V251_CAVPO	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	907
tr A0A6I9JZ04 A0A6I9JZ04_CHRAS	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	911
tr A0A7J7SK29 A0A7J7SK29_RHIFE	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	930
sp P28340 DP0D1_HUMAN	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	906
tr A0A2K6D6G8 A0A2K6D6G8_MACNE	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	929
tr A0A0A0MW23 A0A0A0MW23_PAPAN	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	907
tr A0A452F6S3 A0A452F6S3_CAPHI	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	919
tr A0A6P7EPG1 A0A6P7EPG1_SHEEP	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	908
sp P28339 DP0D1_BOVIN	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	908
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	908
tr A0A383ZY66 A0A383ZY66_BALAS	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	909
tr A0A2Y9P989 A0A2Y9P989_DELLE	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	909
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	909
tr A0A5G2QET9 A0A5G2QET9_PIG	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	929
tr A0A6J1XK42 A0A6J1XK42_ACIBJ	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	909
tr M3VUJ4 M3VUJ4_FELCA	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	909
tr E2R5W5 E2R5W5_CANLF	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	909
tr G1M3J7 G1M3J7_AILME	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	909
tr A0A2U3ZRE1 A0A2U3ZRE1_ODORO	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	909
tr A0A6J2WZ6 A0A6J2WZ6_CHACN	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	913
tr Q2KNE0 Q2KNE0_DANRE	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	913
tr A0A6P6JVN6 A0A6P6JVN6_CARAU	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	913
tr A0A6P6JG77 A0A6P6JG77_CARAU	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	913
tr A0A673JF13 A0A673JF13_9TELE	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	913
tr A0A498LX53 A0A498LX53_LABRO	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	908
tr COHA77 COHA77_SALSA	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	913
tr A0A6P7IUM6 A0A6P7IUM6_9TELE	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	912
tr A0A3Q3E049 A0A3Q3E049_HIPCM	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	913
tr A0A4W3I8L4 A0A4W3I8L4_CALMI	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	914
tr D0VEW7 D0VEW7_XENLA	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	913
tr A0A6J1U352 A0A6J1U352_9SAUR	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	916
tr A0A6I9XX64 A0A6I9XX64_9SAUR	RLLIDRDVPSGVAHAQDVISDLLCNRDISQLVITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVLAERMRRK	919

sp Q9LVN7 DP0D1_ARATH	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLLWT-NPQKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTESLN	846
tr A0A3P6BBX0 A0A3P6BBX0_BRAOL	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLLWT-NPQKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTESLN	841
tr A0A39720B4 A0A39720B4_BRACM	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLLWT-NPQKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTESLN	841
tr A0A07812E2 A0A07812E2_BRANA	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLLWT-NPQKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTESLN	841
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	852
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	872
tr A0A6G1C319 A0A6G1C319_9ORYZ	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	852
sp Q9LRE6 DP0D1_ORYSJ	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	854
tr A0A0E0MDA8 A0A0E0MDA8_ORYPU	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	838
tr A0A5J9USA3 A0A5J9USA3_9POAL	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	849
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	852
tr A0A2S3ICY2 A0A2S3ICY2_9POAL	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	854
tr K3ZGZ6 K3ZGZ6_SEITIT	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	852
tr A0A2P2KVG9 A0A2P2KVG9_RHIMU	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	841
tr A0A7J7DZR4 A0A7J7DZR4_TRIWF	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	836
tr A0A200Q8R4 A0A200Q8R4_9MAGN	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	802
tr A0A2P6RSP9 A0A2P6RSP9_ROSCH	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	839
tr A0A2I4F7Z3 A0A2I4F7Z3_JUGRE	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	836
tr A0A6J5U1U4 A0A6J5U1U4_PRUAR	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	835
tr A0A5E4GBB6 A0A5E4GBB6_PRUUD	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	835
tr A0A6P5S1M3 A0A6P5S1M3_PRUAV	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLYWT-NPEKFDKMDTKGIETVRRDNCPLVKNLVTECLH	835
tr A0A6P5I296 A0A6P5I296_PHACI	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	883
sp P52431 DP0D1_MOUSE	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	847
tr O54747 DP0D1_RAT	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	845
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	845
tr A0A1S3A927 A0A1S3A927_ERIEU	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	849
tr H0V251 H0V251_CAVPO	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	847
tr A0A6I9JZ04 A0A6I9JZ04_CHRAS	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	851
tr A0A7J7SK29 A0A7J7SK29_RHIFE	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	870
sp P28340 DP0D1_HUMAN	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	849
tr A0A2K6D6G8 A0A2K6D6G8_MACNE	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	866
tr A0A0A0MW23 A0A0A0MW23_PAPAN	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	849
tr A0A452F6S3 A0A452F6S3_CAPHI	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	857
tr A0A6P7EPG1 A0A6P7EPG1_SHEEP	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	848
sp P28339 DP0D1_BOVIN	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	848
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	848
tr A0A383ZY66 A0A383ZY66_BALAS	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	849
tr A0A2Y9P989 A0A2Y9P989_DELLE	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	849
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	849
tr A0A5G2QET9 A0A5G2QET9_PIG	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	869
tr A0A6J1XK42 A0A6J1XK42_ACIBJ	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	849
tr M3VUJ4 M3VUJ4_FELCA	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	849
tr E2R5W5 E2R5W5_CANLF	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	849
tr G1M3J7 G1M3J7_AILME	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	849
tr A0A2U3ZRE1 A0A2U3ZRE1_ODORO	IRLEFEKVFYPYLLISKKRYAGLLPSSRSDAHDRMDCKGLEAVRRDNCPLVANLVTSASLR	849
tr A0A6J2WZ6 A0A6J2WZ6_CHACN	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLYPSSAEBHDKMDCKGIETVRRDNCPLVANLINTCLO	853
tr Q2KNE0 Q2KNE0_DANRE	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLYPSSAEBHDKMDCKGIETVRRDNCPLVANLINTCLO	853
tr A0A6P6JVN6 A0A6P6JVN6_CARAU	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLYPSSAEBHDKMDCKGIETVRRDNCPLVANLINTCLO	853
tr A0A6P6JG77 A0A6P6JG77_CARAU	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLYPSSAEBHDKMDCKGIETVRRDNCPLVANLINTCLO	853
tr A0A673JF13 A0A673JF13_9TELE	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLYPSSAEBHDKMDCKGIETVRRDNCPLVANLINTCLO	853
tr A0A498LX53 A0A498LX53_LABRO	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLYPSSAEBHDKMDCKGIETVRRDNCPLVANLINTCLO	848
tr COHA77 COHA77_SALSA	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLYPSSAEBHDKMDCKGIETVRRDNCPLVANLINTCLO	853
tr A0A6P7IUM6 A0A6P7IUM6_9TELE	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLYPSSAEBHDKMDCKGIETVRRDNCPLVANLINTCLO	852
tr A0A3Q3E049 A0A3Q3E049_HIPCM	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLYPSSAEBHDKMDCKGIETVRRDNCPLVANLINTCLO	853
tr A0A4W3I8L4 A0A4W3I8L4_CALMI	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLYPSSAEBHDKMDCKGIETVRRDNCPLVANLINTCLO	854
tr D0VEW7 D0VEW7_XENLA	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLYPSSAEBHDKMDCKGIETVRRDNCPLVANLINTCLO	853
tr A0A6J1U352 A0A6J1U352_9SAUR	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLYPSSAEBHDKMDCKGIETVRRDNCPLVANLINTCLO	856
tr A0A6I9XX64 A0A6I9XX64_9SAUR	IKLEFEKVFYPYLLINKKRYAGLYPSSAEBHDKMDCKGIETVRRDNCPLVANLINTCLO	859

sp	Q9LVN7	DP0D1	ARATH	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IKAAKGAKAYE	RSED	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK	Pol	CTD	
tr	AOA3P6BBX0	AOA3P6BBX0	BRAOL	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			966
tr	AOA39720B4	AOA39720B4	BRACM	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			961
tr	AOA07812E2	AOA07812E2	BRANA	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			961
tr	AOA3B67HK9	AOA3B67HK9	WHEAT	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			972
tr	AOA287NECO	AOA287NECO	HORVV	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			992
tr	AOA6G1C319	AOA6G1C319	9ORYZ	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			958
sp	Q9LRE6	DP0D1	ORYS3	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			974
tr	AOA0E0MDA8	AOA0E0MDA8	ORYPU	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			958
tr	AOA5J9USA3	AOA5J9USA3	9FOAL	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			969
tr	AOA1D6QLT8	AOA1D6QLT8	MAI5E	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			972
tr	AOA2S3IC2	AOA2S3IC2	9POAL	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			972
tr	K3EGZ6	K3EGZ6	SETIT	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			974
tr	AOA2P2KVG9	AOA2P2KVG9	RHIMU	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			961
tr	AOA7J7DER4	AOA7J7DER4	TRIWF	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			956
tr	AOA200Q8R4	AOA200Q8R4	9MAGN	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			922
tr	AOA2P6RSP9	AOA2P6RSP9	ROSCH	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			959
tr	AOA214F7Z3	AOA214F7Z3	JUGRE	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			956
tr	AOA6J5U1U4	AOA6J5U1U4	PRUAR	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			955
tr	AOA5E4GBB6	AOA5E4GBB6	PRUDU	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			955
tr	AOA6P5S1M3	AOA6P5S1M3	PRUAV	RDAATAPNVGDRVPPVVI	IITAANGAKG	YKSESD	PYVLQNNI	PIDPNYLQNI	ISK			955
tr	AOA6P5I296	AOA6P5I296	_PHACI	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				1003
sp	F52431	DP0D1	MOUSE	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				967
sp	O54747	DP0D1	RAT	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				965
tr	G3V8M1	G3V8M1	RAT	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				965
tr	AOA1S3A927	AOA1S3A927	_ERIEU	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				969
tr	HOV251	HOV251	_CAVPO	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				967
tr	AOA6I9J204	AOA6I9J204	_CHRAS	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				971
tr	AOA7J78K29	AOA7J78K29	_RHIFE	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				990
sp	F28340	DP0D1	HUMAN	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				969
tr	AOA2K6D6G8	AOA2K6D6G8	_MACNE	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				966
tr	AOA0A0MW23	AOA0A0MW23	_PAPAN	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				969
tr	AOA452P683	AOA452P683	_CAPHI	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				977
tr	AOA6P7EPG1	AOA6P7EPG1	_SHEEP	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				968
sp	F28339	DP0D1	BOVIN	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				968
tr	E1BN26	E1BN26	_BOVIN	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				968
tr	AOA382Y266	AOA382Y266	_BALAS	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				969
tr	AOA2Y9P989	AOA2Y9P989	_DELLE	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				969
tr	F7DXU3	F7DXU3	_HORSE	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				969
tr	AOA6G2QBT9	AOA6G2QBT9	_FIG	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				969
tr	AOA6J1XK42	AOA6J1XK42	_ACIJB	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				969
tr	M3VUJ4	M3VUJ4	_FELCA	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				969
tr	E2RSW5	E2RSW5	_CANLF	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				969
tr	G1M3J7	G1M3J7	_AILME	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				969
tr	AOA2U32RE1	AOA2U32RE1	_ODORO	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				969
tr	AOA6J2WZ6	AOA6J2WZ6	_CHACN	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				973
tr	Q2KNE0	Q2KNE0	_DANRE	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				973
tr	AOA6P6JVN6	AOA6P6JVN6	_CARAU	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				973
tr	AOA6P6JG77	AOA6P6JG77	_CARAU	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				973
tr	AOA673JF13	AOA673JF13	_STELE	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				973
tr	AOA498LX53	AOA498LX53	_LABRO	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				968
tr	COHA77	COHA77	_SALSA	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				973
tr	AOA6P7IUM6	AOA6P7IUM6	_STELE	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				972
tr	AOA3Q2D49	AOA3Q2D49	_HIPCM	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				973
tr	AOA4W2I8L4	AOA4W2I8L4	_CALMI	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				974
tr	DOVEW7	DOVEW7	_KENLA	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				973
tr	AOA6J1U352	AOA6J1U352	_9SAUR	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				976
tr	AOA6I9XX64	AOA6I9XX64	_9SAUR	RDFGSAPSLGDRVPPVVI	IIGAANGVAA	YKSESD	PLFVLEHSL	PIDTQYVLEQQLAK				979

sp	Q9LVN7	DP0D1	ARATH	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP			
tr	AOA3P6BBX0	AOA3P6BBX0	BRAOL	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1022		
tr	AOA39720B4	AOA39720B4	BRACM	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1017		
tr	AOA07812E2	AOA07812E2	BRANA	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1017		
tr	AOA3B67HK9	AOA3B67HK9	WHEAT	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1030		
tr	AOA287NECO	AOA287NECO	HORVV	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1050		
tr	AOA6G1C319	AOA6G1C319	9ORYZ	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1016		
sp	Q9LRE6	DP0D1	ORYS3	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1032		
tr	AOA0E0MDA8	AOA0E0MDA8	ORYPU	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1016		
tr	AOA5J9USA3	AOA5J9USA3	9FOAL	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1027		
tr	AOA1D6QLT8	AOA1D6QLT8	MAI5E	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1030		
tr	AOA2S3IC2	AOA2S3IC2	9POAL	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1030		
tr	K3EGZ6	K3EGZ6	SETIT	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1032		
tr	AOA2P2KVG9	AOA2P2KVG9	RHIMU	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1019		
tr	AOA7J7DER4	AOA7J7DER4	TRIWF	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1014		
tr	AOA200Q8R4	AOA200Q8R4	9MAGN	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	980		
tr	AOA2P6RSP9	AOA2P6RSP9	ROSCH	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1017		
tr	AOA214F7Z3	AOA214F7Z3	JUGRE	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1014		
tr	AOA6J5U1U4	AOA6J5U1U4	PRUAR	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1013		
tr	AOA5E4GBB6	AOA5E4GBB6	PRUDU	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1013		
tr	AOA6P5S1M3	AOA6P5S1M3	PRUAV	FEPVLKNA	--SRELLHGSHTRS	ISITPSN	SGIMKFAKKQLS	CVGCKVPI	SN--GTLCAS	PIP	1013		
tr	AOA6P5I296	AOA6P5I296	_PHACI	FEPILGEGRAEV	VLLRGDHTRC	KTVLT	GKVV	GGLLA	FAKRRNC	CG	GCRVFLSH--QGA	CKF	1062
sp	F52431	DP0D1	MOUSE	FEPILGEGRAEV	VLLRGDHTRC	KTVLT	GKVV	GGLLA	FAKRRNC	CG	GCRVFLSH--QGA	CKF	1026
sp	O54747	DP0D1	RAT	FEPILGEGRAEV	VLLRGDHTRC	KTVLT	GKVV	GGLLA	FAKRRNC	CG	GCRVFLSH--QGA	CKF	1024
tr	G3V8M1	G3V8M1	RAT	FEPILGEGRAEV	VLLRGDHTRC	KTVLT	GKVV	GGLLA	FAKRRNC	CG	GCRVFLSH--QGA	CKF	1024
tr	AOA1S3A927	AOA1S3A927	_ERIEU	FEPILGEGRAEV	VLLRGDHTRC	KTVLT	GKVV	GGLLA	FAKRRNC	CG	GCRVFLSH--QGA	CKF	1028
tr	HOV251	HOV251	_CAVPO	FEPILGEGRAEV	VLLRGDHTRC	KTVLT	GKVV	GGLLA	FAKRRNC	CG	GCRVFLSH--QGA	CKF	1026
tr	AOA6I9J204	AOA6I9J204	_CHRAS	FEPILGEGRAEV	VLLRGDHTRC	KTVLT	GKVV	GGLLA	FAKRRNC	CG	GCRVFLSH--QGA	CKF	1030
tr	AOA7J78K29	AOA7J78K29	_RHIFE	FEPILGEGRAEV	VLLRGDHTRC	KTVLT	GKVV	GGLLA	FAKRRNC	CG	GCRVFLSH--QGA	CKF	1028
sp	F28340	DP0D1	HUMAN	FEPILGEGRAEV	VLLRGDHTRC	KTVLT	GKVV	GGLLA	FAKRRNC	CG	GCRVFLSH--QGA	CKF	1048
tr	AOA2K6D6G8	AOA2K6D6G8	_MACNE	FEPILGEGRAEV	VLLRGDHTRC	KTVLT	GKVV	GGLLA	FAKRRNC	CG	GCRVFLSH--QGA	CKF	1028
tr	AOA0A0MW23	AOA0A0MW23	_PAPAN	FEPILGEGRAEV	VLLRGDHTRC	KTVLT	GKVV	GGLLA	FAKRRNC	CG	GCRVFLSH--QGA	CKF	1036

Figure 4 Mix and Match MSA of plant and animal delta polymerases

δ Polymerase from Plant Sources

Q9LVN7|DPOD1_ARATH DNA polymerase, *Arabidopsis thaliana*
A0A3P6BBX0_BRAOL DNA polymerase, *Brassica oleracea*
A0A397Z0B4_BRACM DNA polymerase, *Brassica campestris*
A0A078I2E2_BRANA DNA polymerase, *Brassica napus*
A0A287NEC0_HORVV DNA polymerase, *Hordeum vulgare* subsp. *Vulgare*
A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT DNA polymerase, *Triticum aestivum*
A0A6G1C319_9ORYZ DNA polymerase, *Oryza meyeriana* var. *granulate*
Q9LRE6|DPOD1_ORYSJ DNA polymerase, *Oryza sativa* subsp. *Japonica*
A0A0E0MDA8_ORYPU DNA polymerase, *Oryza punctata*
A0A5J9USA3_9POAL DNA polymerase, *Eragrostis curvula*
A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE DNA polymerase, *Zea mays*
A0A2S3ICY2_9POAL DNA polymerase, *Panicum hallii*
K3ZGZ6_SETIT DNA polymerase, *Setaria italic*
A0A2P2KVG9_RHIMU DNA polymerase, *Rhizophora mucronata* (mangrove)
A0A7J7DZR4_TRIWF DNA polymerase, *Tripterygium wilfordii*
A0A200Q8R4_9MAGN DNA polymerase, *Macleaya cordata*
A0A2P6RSP9_ROSCH DNA polymerase, *Rosa chinensis*
A0A2I4F7Z3_JUGRE DNA polymerase, *Juglans regia*
A0A6J5U1U4_PRUAR DNA polymerase, *Prunus armeniaca*
A0A5E4G6B6_PRUDU DNA polymerase, *Prunus dulcis*
A0A6P5S1M3_PRUAV DNA polymerase, *Prunus avium*

δ Polymerase from Animal Sources

A0A6P5IZ96_PHACI DNA polymerase, *Phascolarctos cinereus* (koala bear)
P52431|DPOD1_MOUSE DNA polymerase, *Mus musculus*
O54747|DPOD1_RAT DNA polymerase, *Rattus norvegicus*
G3V8M1_RAT DNA polymerase, *Rattus norvegicus*
A0A1S3A927_ERIEU DNA polymerase, *Erinaceus europaeus*
H0V251_CAVPO DNA polymerase, *Cavia porcellus*
A0A6I9JZ04_CHRAS DNA polymerase, *Chrysochloris asiatica*
A0A7J7SK29_RHIFE DNA polymerase, *Rhinolophus ferrumequinum*
P28340|DPOD1_HUMAN DNA polymerase, *Homo sapiens*
A0A2K6D6G8_MACNE DNA polymerase, *Macaca nemestrina*
A0A0A0MW23_PAPAN DNA polymerase, *Papio Anubis*
A0A452F6S3_CAPHI DNA polymerase, *Capra hircus*
A0A6P7EPG1_SHEEP DNA polymerase, *Ovis aries*
A0A6P7IUM6_9TELE DNA polymerase, *Parambassis ranga*
P28339|DPOD1_BOVIN DNA polymerase, *Bos Taurus*
E1BNZ6_BOVIN DNA polymerase, *Bos Taurus*
A0A383ZY66_BALAS DNA polymerase, *Balaenoptera acutorostrata scammoni* (Minke Whale)
A0A2Y9P989_DELLE DNA polymerase, *Delphinapterus leucas*
F7DXU3_HORSE DNA polymerase, *Equus caballus*
A0A5G2QET9_PIG DNA polymerase, *Sus scrofa*
A0A6J1U352_9SAUR DNA polymerase, *Notechis scutatus* (Tiger snake)
M3VUJ4_FELCA DNA polymerase, *Felis catus*
E2R5W5_CANLF DNA polymerase, *Canis lupus familiaris*
G1M3J7_AILME DNA polymerase, *Ailuropoda melanoleuca*
A0A2U3ZRE1_ODORO DNA polymerase, *Odobenus rosmarus divergens*
A0A6J2WZW6_CHACN DNA polymerase, *Chanos chanos*
Q2KNE0_DANRE DNA polymerase, *Danio rerio*
A0A6P6JVN6_CARAU DNA polymerase, *Carassius auratus*
A0A6P6JG77_CARAU DNA polymerase, *Carassius auratus*
A0A673JFI3_9TELE DNA polymerase, *Sinocyclocheilus rhinoceros*
A0A498LX53_LABRO DNA polymerase, *Labeo rohita*
C0HA77_SALSA DNA polymerase, *Salmo salar*
A0A3Q3E049_HIPCM DNA polymerase, *Hippocampus comes*
A0A4W3I8L4_CALMI DNA polymerase, *Callorhinchus milii*
D0VEW7_XENLA DNA polymerase, *Xenopus laevis*
A0A6J1U352_9SAUR DNA polymerase, *Notechis scutatus*
A0A6I9XX64_9SAUR DNA polymerase, *Thamnophis sirtalis* (Garter snake)

3.2. Active Site Analyses of the δ DNA Polymerases

The MSA analysis of the DNA-dependent DNA pols (DdDps) from viruses, bacteria, yeasts, higher fungi, plants and animals has shown that the δ pols of eukaryotes are closer to viral and prokaryotic DNA pols in possessing the two characteristic invariant motifs, -SLYPS- and -YGD TDS-. Even though all three eukaryotic replicative pols (pols α , ϵ and δ) are classified under the B-family pols, the pol ϵ differs from others by not possessing the conserved -SLYPS- and -YGD TDS- motifs, suggesting their possible different evolutionary origins. The proposed active site amino acids at the pol and PR domains are shown in Table 1. The template-binding pair (YG), the catalytic basic amino acid (K) and nucleotide selection amino acid (Q) are completely conserved in both the replicative δ pols from plants and animals. The PR 3'→5' exonuclease belongs to the DEDD-superfamily of exonucleases reported from other DNA polymerases as well. The proposed PR exonuclease active site amino acids that are confirmed by SDM experiments are highlighted in dark blue (Table 1).

Table 1 Comparative analysis of the DNA δ pols from yeasts, plants and animals

	Yeasts (<i>S. cerevisiae</i>)	Plants (<i>A. Thaliana</i>)	Animals (Human)
PR exonuclease	D ³²³ E ³²³ F ⁴⁰⁷Y ⁵¹⁶D ⁵²⁰ .	-DIE ³¹⁴FD ⁴⁵⁴Y ⁵⁰⁷D ⁵¹¹ .	D ³¹⁶ E ³¹⁸ F ⁴⁰²Y ⁵¹¹ D ⁵¹⁵ .
Pol δ	⁻⁶⁸⁸ FKRDVNLNGR Q ⁴ LAL K ¹ SANSV Y ⁸ GFT ¹¹ -	-EKAVLDGR Q ⁴ LAL K ¹ SANSV Y ⁸ GFT-	⁻⁶⁸¹ LRRQVLDG Q ⁴ LAL K ¹ V SANSV Y ⁸ GFT-
-YGD TDS- & -SLYPS-	⁻⁶¹⁰ N SLYPS ^{616-&-759} V YGD TDS ^{V766-}	⁻⁶⁰² A SLYPS ^{608-&-750} V YGD TDS ^{SV757-}	⁻⁶⁰⁴ S SLYPS ^{610-&-752} V YGD TDS ^{V759-}

Adapted from Palanivelu [6]. Amino acids, highlighted in dark-blue, are confirmed by SDM analysis.

Pol δ is a versatile PR enzyme. As mentioned earlier, it can correct not only its own errors but also the errors made by the other two replication enzymes, viz. DNA pol α and pol ϵ and thus, ensuring an error-free replication process. The PR active site amino acids of the δ pols, arrived at from MSA analysis by sequence similarity, were also further corroborated by SDM analysis. Simon *et al.*, [16] subjected the **D** and **E** of the first conserved triad of the PR active site of pol δ of the yeast enzyme, (i.e.), -**D**³²¹**E**³²³- to **D**³²¹→A/V and **E**³²³→A and also in the **D** in the dyad, **FD**⁴⁰⁷→A by SDM. They found that these mutations drastically reduced the exonuclease activity, suggesting their direct role in the PR function. Importantly, their SDM experiments on the above PR active site amino acids did not affect the pol activity, suggesting that both the domains are well separated. Consistent with the key role played by pol δ in DNA replication, inactivation of pol δ PR function or mutation of critical pol δ residues involved in base selection, resulted in a dramatic increase in replication errors in both yeast and mice enzymes [14 and references therein].

Figures 5A and 5B show the proposed active site of the PR exonucleases from animals and plants. The proposed two-metal ion in the active sites is based on findings of similar active site structure in the 3'→5' exonuclease active site in *E. coli* DNA pol I [17], and such similarities are also extensively analyzed and reported by this author from various sources [18]. The mechanism of Zn-mediated excision of the wrong nucleotide incorporation is explained by Palanivelu [4].

Figure 5 Proposed amino acids at the PR exonuclease active sites of the DNA pols δ from animals, **5A** (from humans) and **5B** from plants, (*A. thaliana*) (numberings are from the humans and *A. thaliana* δ pols).

3.3. The Importance of CysA, CysB and PIP in the Eukaryotic Replicative δ Polymerases

The importance of these three motifs is understood from the analysis of the replicative pols of other eukaryotes as well. All the three eukaryotic replicative pols (pol α , ϵ and δ) invariably possess two of the conserved ZBMs, viz. CysA and CysB, in the CTD of their catalytic subunits and a PIP in the δ pols, suggesting their important role(s) in eukaryotic genome replication. The CysA is the regular ZBM whereas at the CysB, another Zn²⁺ binds and forms the 4Fe-4S cluster.

The importance of these motifs is proved by SDM and X-ray crystallographic analyses. Based on spectroscopic and other experimental data, Jain et al., [19] have shown that the three highly conserved Cys residues (Cys⁶⁶⁵, Cys⁶⁷⁷ and Cys⁷⁶³) of yeast pol ϵ are involved in binding to the Fe-S cluster. This was based on their observation that the wild-type yeast pol ϵ 's catalytic core was found to be yellowish-brown, but the mutant in which all three Cs, (Cys⁶⁶⁵, Cys⁶⁷⁷ and Cys⁷⁶³) were mutated, it became colourless. Besides, they also found that a Cys triple mutant was deficient in the DNA pol activity, but not in the exonuclease activity, suggesting a link between the pol activity and the Fe-S cluster. A similar SDM experiment on pol δ by Netz et al, [20] has shown that the CysB motif was bound to [4Fe-4S] cluster to form an active pol complex. For example, the loss of the [4Fe-4S] cluster by a Cys-ligand mutagenesis in pol δ , destabilized the CTD and abolished interaction with the polD1 and polD2 subunits. This was further confirmed by SDM experiments, where the conversion of the C residues, viz. C¹⁰⁵⁶, C¹⁰⁵⁹, C¹⁰⁶⁹, C¹⁰⁷⁴ (in yeast pol δ) to Ala abolished Fe-S binding [20]. In addition to, a lethal double mutation, C¹⁰⁵⁹→S/C¹⁰⁷⁴→S in CysB of pol δ disrupted binding polD1 and polD2, but in marked contrast, a lethal double mutation of CysA (C¹⁰¹²→S/C¹⁰²⁷→S) did not alter the subunit composition of the pol δ complex, and also did not affect the pol δ interactions in the yeast two-hybrid analysis. These authors have further shown that the Zn-binding CysA motif is required for PCNA-mediated pol δ processivity. The PCNA interactions with PIP enhance the pol δ activity several folds. However, the PIP is found only in the δ pols.

3.4. The Unique -SLYPS- and -YGD TDS- Motifs of δ Polymerases

As discussed elsewhere, the -SLYPS- and -YGD TDS- are the characteristic motifs found only in the replicative pols α and δ . They are implicated in dNTP- and metal-binding, respectively. Interestingly, they are also reported from a large number of DdDps from viruses and bacteria [4,6]. For example, in addition to their presence in the eukaryotic replicative DNA pols α and δ , they are also found in the *E. coli* DNA pol II and in many viral DNA pols like pox viruses (Smallpox, Monkeypox, etc.), Vaccinia, Epstein-Barr virus, Human Cytomegalo virus, Human Herpes Simplex Viruses 1 and 2, Adeno virus 2, *E. coli* phage RB69, *Bacillus subtilis* phage Φ 29, suggesting their possible origin from viruses and prokaryotes. Interestingly, these two motifs are also completely conserved in the δ pol from various plant sources. In contrast, they are not found in the eukaryotic leading-strand synthesis enzyme, the pol ϵ . In fact, the other eukaryotic replicase enzyme, viz. pol ϵ , is closer to the prokaryotic DNA pols I, and DNA pols III (in the catalytic subunit α of the replicases), where they also do not possess these two motifs, strongly suggesting two different origins of the eukaryotic replicative pols. Thus, based on this property, DNA pols maybe broadly classified into two groups, i.e., the one having these two characteristic motifs in them, like prokaryotic DNA pol II, α , δ and ζ pols and the other group which does not possess these two motifs, like pol ϵ , prokaryotic DNA pol I, and DNA pol III (prokaryotic replicases).

SLYPS and YGD TDS motifs' role in dNTP- and metal-binding sites, respectively, has been further confirmed by SDM experiments. The conserved motif -YGD T D¹⁰⁰⁴S- in the catalytic subunit of the human DNA pol α was subjected to SDM analysis. The D¹⁰⁰⁴→N mutation produced a protein with no detectable pol activity while other SDM mutants at that site showed activities from 1 to 20% of the wild-type pol activity [21]. The second conserved motif's (-SLYPS-) involvement in dNTP-binding is also proved by similar SDM experiments using the yeast pol δ . The SDM analysis where L⁶¹²→G in the -SL⁶¹²YPS- motif of yeast pol δ , increased the rates of C-to-A transversion substitutions [22], suggesting its importance in the nucleotide selection process. Furthermore, they also reported that the substitutions at L⁶¹² of *S. cerevisiae* δ pol differentially affect viability, sensitivity to genotoxic agents, cell cycle progression, and replication fidelity.

Moreover, substitution at a residue in the conserved motif A (-SLYPS-) caused mutator phenotypes in eukaryotic DNA pol δ [23]. They have generated mice harbouring an L⁶⁰⁴→G or L⁶⁰⁴→K substitutions in the highly conserved -SL⁶⁰⁴YPS- in the active site of mice δ pol. They found that the homozygous *Pold1*^{L604G/L604G} and *Pold1*^{L604K/L604K} mice died in utero. However, heterozygous animals were viable and displayed no overall increase in disease incidence, indicative of efficient compensation for the defective mutant pol. Schmitt *et al.*, analyzed the human δ pol and found that the mutation of the highly conserved L⁶⁰⁶ in the -SL⁶⁰⁶YPS- motif induced a mutator phenotype with a biased error spectrum that would be suitable for strand-specific identification of pol δ mediated DNA transactions *in vivo* [24]. The above experiments have shown unambiguously the importance of these motifs in δ pols.

Pavlov *et al.*, 2001 [25] analyzed the crucial Y in α , δ , ϵ , and ζ in the yeast DNA pols. They replaced the Y with A in the catalytic subunits of DNA pols α , δ , ϵ , and ζ and examined the consequences *in vivo*. Strains with the Y→A substitution in

the conserved -SL/MYPS/N- motif in the pols δ and ϵ were inviable. Strains with the same substitution in Rev3, the catalytic subunit of pol ζ , were nearly UV immutable, suggesting severe loss of its function. Their experiment further suggested that the Y in the conserved -SL/MYPS/N- motif- is important for the functioning of all B-family pols.

4. Conclusion

MSA analysis has shown that one of the main replicative δ pols from plants and animals contains the same template-binding pairs, catalytic and nucleotide selection amino acids, and also very similar catalytic metal-binding motifs. The highly conserved CTDs in both pols also suggest a similar role in the regulation of the replication process. Moreover, the PR exonuclease active site amino acids are found to be identical in both plants and animals and belong to the DEDD(Y)-superfamily of PR exonucleases. These findings establish that the catalytic, PR exonuclease and CTD domains of the δ pols and their roles in genome replication are highly conserved across all eukaryotes, like yeasts, higher fungi, plants and animals. Moreover, the highly conserved pol, PR exonuclease and CTD domains in plant and animal replicative δ pols strongly suggest a possible common evolutionary origin.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

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